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**ALDO LEOPOLD'S LAND ETHIC AND THE PARADOX OF
NIGERIA'S INTENDED PLAN TO RESUME OIL EXTRACTION IN
OGONI.**

ABSTRACT

The impact of Nigeria's oil extraction on the environment, livelihood, health of the oil-bearing communities in the Niger Delta is a known fact. Extraction of oil and hydrocarbon brought conflict, death and misery to the people on whose land oil is drilled. Only a few influential and opportune elite benefit from the oil proceed. While countries like Saudi Arabia, Russia, Canada, United States, Iraq, United Arab Emirates, Kuwait, and Norway have made ground-breaking innovations in the infrastructure and human development of its peoples from oil exploitation, Nigeria remains in squalor and decay after five decades of oil extraction. This paper resonates Aldo Leopold's Land ethic vis-a-vis the enigma of Nigeria's oil exploitation in Ogoni. Oil drilling in Ogoni was halted in 1993 due to disruptions from local agitations against imminent environmental pollution and ecological destruction. It is envisioned that the Nigerian government's recent intention to resume oil extraction in Ogoni without a conclusive negotiation and dialogue with the local communities who are still suffering from decades of the negative impact of oil exploitation is ill-conceived and might trigger fresh waves of chaos and insurrection. The paper adopts hermeneutics in critically analyzing the philosophical views of Leopold, and the anthropocentric and biocentric interpretations of philosophers. It recommends that the Nigerian government should first and foremost begin to gradually implement the global energy transition plan in a manner that the local Ogoni communities would adopt an energy source that they can own, an energy that is clean, sustainable, and devoid of pollution.

Keywords: Land Ethic, Oil Extraction, Pollution, Anthropocentric, Biocentric, Energy Transition.

INTRODUCTION

Conservation and many other contemporary environmental movements would not have risen if the land did not experience environmental injustice. In Ogoni, for the past five decades, there have been huge extraction of crude oil and resources that are beyond the limit that nature can accommodate. Oil was exploited without recourse to the Nigerian laws and regulations. It is exploitation that violates the land and threatens the needs of the generations yet unborn. Oil exploitation caused the displacement of indigenous people. However, with the rise of environmental ethics and philosophers in the early 20th century, there was a reaction against the mistreatment of the land. Several thinkers, such as John Muir, Gifford Pinchot, Henry David Thoreau and Aldo Leopold, and Ken Saro-Wiwa, to name a few, have purposely established ideas to enlighten and change the way society views the land and the environment. This paved the way to an apparent multiplicity of thoughts and groups who claimed to fight for environmental rights and to morally consider the land and the environment. Despite the abundance of such point of view, the focus of this research rests on the thoughts of the American philosopher Aldo Leopold's Concept of Conservation vis-à-vis the Ogoni environmental debacle. In Nigeria, the indigenous Ogoni were the first people to agitate against oil and gas exploration and its attended land and environmental degradation.

The Ogoni people are a distinct indigenous minority nationality living in an area of 404 square miles (about 100,000 square kilometers) on the south eastern fringe of the Niger Delta River in what is geo-politically referred today as the South-South of Nigeria. The Ogoni people number around 750,000 based on the last census and has a population density of 1250, one of the very highest in any rural setting of the world and compares favorably with the Nigeria national average of 250 (Saro-Wiwa, 1992).

As an indigenous people, the Ogoni had a well-established social system that placed great value on the environment before the advent of British colonial rule. Living on a fertile alluvial soil and blessed with a necklace of rivers and creeks, the Ogoni people seized the opportunity of having these resources to become great fisher folks and farmers, producing not only for their own subsistence but also for their neighbours in the Niger Delta and was appropriately referred to as the 'Food basket of the Niger Delta'. They created a system of agriculture; their traditional means of livelihood ensured the sustainable management and sustainable exploitation of natural resources. Socio-culturally, the Ogoni people live in closely knit communities and are more endogenous. The

Ogoni people have a tradition and custom that is deeply rooted in nature and this helped them to protect and preserve the environment for generations. The land on which they live and the rivers which surround them are viewed by them not just as natural resources for exploitation but with deep spiritual significance. "Land is viewed as the abode of our ancestors from where they oversee our lives, it is also a god and we revere it as such" (Saro-Wiwa, 1986). This respect and reverence for land also means that forests are not merely a collection of trees and the abode of animals but also, and more intrinsically, a sacred possession. Therefore, trees in the forests cannot be cut indiscriminately without regard to their sacrosanctity and their influence on the well-being of the entire community. There are some animals that you cannot kill because they are said to be totems. That is, they are supposed to be animations of the spirit of somebody and if you kill them, then something disastrous will happen.

Similarly, rivers and streams, apart from being the source of water for life, are also intricately bound up with the life of the community and are not to be desecrated. Thus, the Ogonis believe that there is a dynamic interaction that exists between men and women, animal, plants, etc. These were the natural rights that the Ogonis understood over the years and there is a belief in the system that every person has to take action to protect those natural rights. Rights to lands, rights to nature etc.

Hence, grave consequences follow any erring human conduct or action desecrating the environment. In the light of this, the Ogonis believe that failure by the custodian community to take action to protect it from desecration attracts the wrath of the gods, which visits the community with disaster (Saro-Wiwa, 1992). The pre-colonial social system therefore ensured sustainable exploitation of natural resource and protection of biodiversity. Most of these practices still exist to this day and this explains why the Ogoni people are unanimous when it comes to taking decisions that borders on their environment. To them, their lives are intrinsically bound with the survival of the environment. This also explains why the Movement for the Survival of the Ogoni People (MOSOP) recorded a phenomenal success in mobilizing the Ogoni People to stand up against the denigration of their environment in the early 1990s.

Oil was discovered in the Ogoni territory in early 1957 when Shell found oil in the Ogoni community of K-Dere popularly and misnomerly called the Bomu Oil fields (Pyagbara, 2005). Subsequently, Shell made more discoveries in other Ogoni communities including Ebubu, Yorla, Bodo West and Korokoro. Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) is the sole player in the oil

extractive industry in Ogoni having secured the Oil Mining License (OML) covering the entire Ogoniland. At the last count, Ogoni has five major oil fields with 110 oil wells, hooked up to five flow stations at Bomu, Korokoro, Yorla, Bodo West and Ebubu by a necklace of interconnecting pipelines which criss-crossed Ogoni villages (Pyagbara, 2005). Gas had been flared for 24 hours a day for 40 years in close proximity to human habitation in nineteen oil locations in a 404 square mile area with population density of 1250 per square mile. This have been done without due regard to the negative impacts of such activities on the people and the environment. Until now, no EIA study in Ogoni has been done (Pyagbara, 2005). Unfortunately, the history of oil exploitation in Ogoni is like the history of oil pollution as the commencement of oil exploration and exploitation was followed almost immediately with the three major causes of oil pollution namely, the impact of the seismic survey, gas flaring and oil spills (Pyagbara, 2004).

This paper, therefore, intends to explore Aldo Leopold's Land Ethic and use it as a critique on the Nigerian oil enterprise on the land and environment, livelihood and health of the people of the Ogoni. The paper critically appraises the Ogoni civil disobedience as a noble option to secure their land and environment. The Ogonis are unique in Nigeria. They took the laws into their hands. They stopped oil exploration for three decades. Since the middle of the 1990s no drop of oil has been extracted from Ogoni. The present government of President Bola Tinubu is presently in dialogue with the Ogoni elite to resume oil exploitation without healing the past wounds. This research brands this adventure a paradox that will that would resonate another round of conflict and further accentuate the already degraded land and environment.

ALDO LEOPOLD'S LAND ETHICS

A land ethic is a philosophy or theoretical framework about how, ethically, humans should regard the land. The term was coined by Aldo Leopold (1887–1953) in his *A Sandy County Almanac* (1943), a classic text of the environmental movement. In the text, he argues that there is a critical need for a "new ethic", an "ethic dealing with human's relation to land and to the animals and plants which grow upon it" (Leopold, 1949) Leopold offers an ecologically based land ethic that rejects strictly human-centred views of the environment and focuses on the preservation of healthy, self-renewing ecosystems. A Sand County Almanac was the first systematic presentation of a holistic or ecocentric approach to the environment (Leopold, 1949). Although Leopold is credited with coining the term "land ethic", there are many

philosophical theories that speak to how humans should treat the land. Some of the most prominent land ethics include those rooted in economics, utilitarianism, libertarianism, egalitarianism, and ecology.

Economics-based land ethic

This is a land ethic based wholly upon economic self-interest (Leopold, 2012). Leopold sees two flaws in this type of ethic. First, he argues that most members of an ecosystem have no economic worth. For this reason, such an ethic can ignore or even eliminate these members when they are actually not necessary for the health of the biotic community of their land. And second, it tends to relegate conservation necessary for healthy ecosystems to the government and these tasks are too large and dispersed to be adequately addressed by such an institution. This ties directly into the context within which Leopold wrote *A Sand County Almanac*.

Leopold proposes the construction of an ecological system. This would distinguish between “social” and “anti-social conduct,” and would encourage a cooperative view of humankind’s place in the natural world (Leopold, 1949). He gives a brief history of ethics. At first, ethics concerned behaviour between individual people. Eventually it extended to include the relationship between individual people and the society in which they lived. Leopold proposes extending ethics one step further, to include people’s relationship to “land and to the animals and plants which grow upon it... the land ethic simply assumes the community extends to include the natural world—soils, waters, plants, animals, or collectively: the land” (Leopold, 1949). Leopold points out that, at present, society’s relationship with the land is economical, not ethical. However, he thinks ethics are an “ecological necessity.” They would serve as a kind of guide for future behaviour and policy. Where “animal instincts” guide an individual’s behaviour, he argues ethics create a “community instinct” (Leopold, 1949). Again, Leopold admits that a land ethic cannot prevent the use or alteration of the land, but it can help protect it from destruction. A land ethic ideally makes humans feel as though they are respectful citizens of the land-community, not conquerors. He criticizes what he sees as an educated view that the earth exists to be exploited by humankind. To him, many people assume that experts and scientists know what is best for the environment. However, Leopold challenges the idea that humans always know what is best for themselves and for the land they inhabit (Leopold, 1949).

Leopold discusses the European settlement of the Mississippi Valley, which taxed the land in such a way that it created an ecological void that was filled by the now famous Kentucky bluegrass. In contrast, in the Southwest, grazing animals ate so many native plants that they degraded the land and the soil, causing erosion which led to further destruction of plants. He therefore argues that if humans cannot even predict how their behaviour will affect the landscape and the soil, they are hardly qualified to make decisions about the landscape's future. He contrasts the Europeans' treatment of the American landscapes with the Pueblo Indians' treatment of the land which, perhaps because they didn't have grazing animals, was less detrimental to the soil's health. He also discusses parts of India that have preserved the landscape by cutting sod for cows to eat, as opposed to letting them graze freely.

Leopold hopes "the concept of land as a community" will soon "penetrate our intellectual life" (Leopold, 19949). He is unhappy that conservation has not fully caught on. He thinks it is an issue not just of "volume" or education but of "content." He thinks conservation is taught as though it is a simple matter of voting and leaving the rest up to the government. He complains that this style of conservation "assigns no obligation" and "calls for no sacrifice" (Leopold, 1949).

Leopold shares a story about farmers in Wisconsin who were bribed into working to preserve the topsoil for five years with free labour and materials from the government. However, when the five years were up, the farmers stopped maintaining their conservationist practices. The Wisconsin legislature thought perhaps farmers would be more motivated to maintain the environment if they wrote their own rules, but after turning over land-use legislation to the farmers, the farmers never wrote a rule to improve their treatment of the land. The only choices farmers made to save the soil were those that were also profitable and convenient, like renovating pastures and not grazing or cultivating hills that could easily erode from overuse.

Leopold categorizes various substitutes for the land ethic he has observed. Economic substitutes are risky because most organisms, or "members of the land community," have no economic value. Often, plants or animals are seen as having no importance unless they have economic value. Although Leopold finds this upsetting, he is happy that there seems to be a shift towards recognizing the "biotic right" of plants and animals to exist (Leopold, 1949). Similarly, Leopold notes that predators have only recently been seen to have value.

Leopold observes that American conservation gives much responsibility to the government. Leopold wonders if this is a sustainable model financially and logistically. He worries the government is too big to deal with the minutiae of land management, and again circles back to an ideal of a national (or global) land ethic, which would require every citizen to do their part to treat the land as a community. He concludes that a purely economic system overlooks the unquantifiable, or economically valueless, elements of a landscape. Furthermore, he thinks the government is ill-equipped to oversee conservation, and instead believes that private landowners need to embrace their ethical obligation to the land.

Leopold believes humans can “be ethical only in relation to something we can see, feel, understand, love, or otherwise have faith in” (Leopold, 1949). To try and make the land seem more accessible, or more tangible, Leopold proposes the idea of a “landmark pyramid.” This is a visualization of the land as a physical pyramid. Energy flows from soil, on the bottom of the pyramid, to plants, insects, birds and rodents, and finally to apex predators, at the top of the pyramid. Each level of the landmark pyramid eats and receives energy from organisms on the level below, except for plants, which also receive energy from sunlight. Within the food pyramid are additional food chains and food webs, “lines of dependency” that determine which animals eat what.

When the earth was younger, the landmark pyramid was simpler, but as more species have evolved it has gotten higher. Leopold argues that “the trend of evolution” is to “diversify the biota,” (Leopold, 1949) and therefore extend the land pyramid upwards. Changes in one part of the pyramid change the entire system. Sometimes the pyramid can adjust, when a change is on a slow, evolutionary scale, but it is harder to recalibrate to man-made changes, which were—and continue to be—of “unprecedented violence, rapidity, and scope” (Leopold, 1949). This idea of the land pyramid growing throughout history contrasts with the present-day land pyramid, which is constantly being attacked as different species become endangered or extinct due to human intervention. Although the pyramid can adapt to change on a geological scale, it is harder for it to restructure itself on a manmade timeline. Leopold lists a few changes humankind has brought to the landmark pyramid, including the elimination of many apex predators, thereby shortening food chains. These changes also include agricultural practices, which strip the soil of its fertility, and polluting the water, which flows back into the pyramid and feeds its plants and animals.

Consequently, Leopold proposes that looking at “land as an energy circuit” is useful for three reasons: first, because it shows “land is not merely soil”; second, because it shows that native plants and animals help maintain a system, whereas invasive or non-native organisms may not; third, because it demonstrates how changes wrought by humans are often much more violent and impactful than slower, natural, evolutionary changes (Leopold, 1949).

Leopold has two primary questions: can the land adjust to manmade changes; and can the changes be enacted in a less violent way? Although he notices that many people believe an “indefinite increase” in human density will enrich the quality of human life, he disagrees. Instead, less dense populations will enact less violent changes on the environment. Leopold thinks it is essential that people love, respect, and admire the land. Only then can they see its non-economic value. He worries that the current economic and educational system teaches people to “outgrow” a love of the landscape (Leopold, 1949).

Leopold’s proposed solution is to stop thinking about land-use as an economic issue. Instead, questions about the land should be considered “in terms of what is ethically and aesthetically right” (Leopold, 1949). He goes on to say that “a thing is right when it tends to preserve the integrity, stability, and beauty of the biotic community” (Leopold, 1972). Leopold acknowledges that economics will always influence land-use, but he believes that it does not determine land use totally. Leopold hopes that a land ethic can and will develop in America. Although he has set down some proposed rules, he understands that an ethic is a constantly evolving, organic concept that can soon be applied to all land use.

LAND ETHIC VIS-À-VIS IMPACT OF THE NIGERIAN OIL ENTERPRISE ON THE ENVIRONMENT, LIVELIHOOD AND HEALTH OF OGONI PEOPLE

Unregulated oil exploration in Ogoni, has led to significant environmental damage, health hazards, loss of livelihood and social unrest. Activities like gas flaring and incessant oil spills from corroded oil pipelines degraded the Ogoni ecosystems, contaminated the rivers and soil, leading to total loss of traditional livelihoods and health hazards (UNEP, 2011). In *Genocide in Nigeria: The Ogoni Tragedy* (1992), Ken Saro-Wiwa explored the intricate connection between oil politics in Nigeria and environmental despoliation in Ogoni. His ideas on the subject interject through most of his writings, including his detention diary, *A Month and A Day* (1995). A corollary theme to environmental destruction for him was political corruption, which he

captured in *A Forest of Flowers* (1986). He also reflected in his civil war journal, *On A Darkling Plain* (1989) his conviction about how the international capitalism of the oil multinationals cooperated with the environmental ethnicism of Nigeria's federal government to turn Ogoniland into an ecological disaster and consigned the people to abject poverty, starvation and death. Ogoni has suffered and continues to suffer the degrading effects of oil exploration and exploitation. Lands, streams and creeks are totally and continually polluted. The atmosphere is contaminated with hydrocarbons, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide.

Most communities experience the infernal quaking caused by gas flares which have been burning 24 hours a day for 33 years (Saro-Wiwa, 1992). Acid rain, oil spillages and blow-outs are common. The results of such unchecked environmental pollution and degradation are that (i) The Ogoni can no longer farm successfully. Once the food basket of the eastern Niger delta, the Ogoni now buy food (when they can afford it); (ii) Fish, once a common source of protein, is now rare. Owing to the constant and continual pollution of streams and creeks, fish can only be caught in deeper and offshore waters for which the Ogoni are not equipped. (iii) All wildlife is dead. (iv) The ecology is changing fast. The mangrove tree, the aerial roots of which normally provide a natural and welcome habitat for many a sea food – crabs, periwinkles, mudskippers, cockles, mussels, shrimps, and all – is now being gradually replaced by unknown and otherwise useless palms. (v) The health hazards generated by an atmosphere charged with hydrocarbon vapour, carbon monoxide and carbon dioxide are innumerable (Saro-Wiwa, 1992).

The event of oil extraction in Ogoni of the Niger Delta in Nigeria is an extended, complicated and often painful one, that to this date has become apparently perverse in terms of its resolution and future alliances (UNEP, 2011). The episodes have become a development that has put local oil-bearing communities, the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) and the International Oil Companies (IOCs) at loggerheads, resulting in a perverse lack of trust, animosity and hostility. The FGN and IOCs on one hand and the local oil-bearing communities on the other hand (Wat, 2004). Decades of dialogues, initiatives and demonstrations have in the long run failed to proffer a solution that meets the expectations of parties (Mmon, 2015). Oil extraction in Ogoni began in the 1950s and wide-ranging production facilities were established within three decades of application. These tasks were handled by Shell Petroleum Development Company (Nigeria) Ltd (SPDC), a joint undertaking between the Nigerian National Petroleum Company (NNPC), Shell International, Elf and AGIP

(NDDC, 2001). The FGN is in joint-venture pacts with the IOCs functional in the oil and gas sector in Nigeria. The FGN has possession of and controls the land with its natural properties in the subsoil. This is a main cause of conflict in Ogoni. Land can be obtained by the government for important public purposes by virtue of the Land Use Act 1978. This law disposed the indigenous Ogoni communities of their land for the use of the FGN. This law contradicts Leopold's libertarianism, a philosophical approach often used to guide actions when making (or not making) changes to the land (Leopold, 1949).

Roughly, libertarianism is the ethical view that communities own themselves and have particular moral rights, including the right to acquire property (Leopold 1949). In a looser sense, libertarianism is commonly identified with the belief that each individual person has a right to a maximum amount of freedom or liberty when this freedom does not interfere with other people's freedom. For right-libertarians, property rights are natural rights. Thus, it would be acceptable for local farmers and fishers to plant and fish on their land and waters as long as this action does not limit the freedom of his or her neighbours. In the case of the Ogoni on the contrary, the FGN forcefully collect their land and mortgage them to the IOCs for oil and gas exploitation without adhering to their own environmental regulation, or the global best practice that they know. This contradicts Leopold's ecologically based land ethics, which is based upon the principle that the land (and the organisms that live off the land) has intrinsic value (Leopold, 1949). These ethics are based on ecological systems. This position was first put forth by Ayers Brinser in *Our Use of the Land*, published in 1939. Brinser argued that white settlers brought with them "the seeds of a civilization which has grown by consuming the land, that is, a civilization which has used up the land in much the same way that a furnace burns coal" (Ayers, 1939).

In Ogoni, three main sources of oil pollution arisen from oil extraction have been identified. These are;

1. Oil spills
2. Gas Flares
3. Effluent and waste discharges.

Oil spills Occurrences

In Ogoni, between 1993 and mid- 2023, there has been a recorded incidences of oil spills. Shell admitted to nearly 14,000 tons (about 100,000 barrels) of oil spilled in Ogoni in 2009. In 2020 and 2021, National Oil Spill Detection Response Agency (NOSDRA) recorded 822 spills in Nigeria's Ogoniland, totalling 28,003 barrels (Amnesty International and Al Jazeera). This is aside from the unnoticed slicks and unreported cases of oil spills. The causes of the spill incidences in Ogoni include pipelines and flow lines leakage, blowouts from well-heads due to poor maintenance and oil spills from flow stations. Oil spills involve the release of dangerous hydrocarbons such as benzene and Polynuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbons into the soil and water sources (Pyagbara, 2024). These spillages affect vast stretches of land and waterways thus polluting not only crops but also marine life and the sources of water for domestic uses. Mangrove forests are particularly vulnerable to oil spills because the soils soak up the oil like sponges and re-release it every rainy season. In other cases, the oil prevents the lenticels of the mangrove to absorb oxygen hence oxygen starvation results. The mangrove withers and dies in large numbers due to oil spill. As the oil spill occurs, it spreads onto farmlands and waterbodies. The toxic crude seeps into the grounds and is taken up by the roots of plants. Recent studies have shown that oil spills lower soil fertility and cause poor growth of plants (Extractive Industries and ESCR, 2000).

Gas Flares

Oil production involves the burning of hydrocarbon gases. The flaring–off of natural or associated gas is done as a by-product of the drilling of crude oil from reservoirs in which oil and gas are mixed. One hundred percent of the gases were being flared, resulting in pollution of the area. This made the Ogoni area one of the most polluted areas in the world. In the Ogoni area, the impact of gas flares on the local ecology and climate as well as peoples' health and property are evident (Mmon, 2015). The flares involve the release of dangerous hydrocarbon mostly methane and others which include sulphureous oxides and the oxides of Nitrogen into the atmosphere. The flares raise the temperature of the surrounding environment to temperatures beyond normal of 13-14,000 degrees Celsius and causing noise pollution around the vicinity of the flares. The result of this unchecked emission of gases is the release of 35 million tons of Carbon dioxide and 12 million tons of methane which means that the Nigerian oilfields contribute more to global warming than the rest of the world put together (NACGOND Report, 2015). Another problem associated with gas

flaring is Light Pollution. Light pollution subjects the living organism around the vicinity of the gas flare to 24-hour daylight. This affects night-time patterns in humans and animals. The flares drive away games, it affects the reproduction of fish as well as sending fish to deep sea areas. The gases released during gas-flaring, mixes with the moisture and other forms of precipitation in the atmosphere to form acid rain (Essential Action Report, 2018).

Effluent and Waste discharges.

Another source of oil related pollution is the discharge of effluents into the surrounding environment, sometimes into the water, by the IOCs. For instance, during exploration or seismic surveys by oil companies, drill cuttings, drilling mud and fluids are used for stimulating production. There is also the use of chemicals during seismic activities. The major constituents of drill cuttings such as baryotes and bentonitic clays when dumped on the ground prevent local plant growth until natural processes develop new topsoil. In the water, these materials are dispersed and sink and may kill local bottom living plants and animals by burying them (Essential Action Report, 2018). In addition to the pollutants introduced into the environment from exploration and exploitation operations, refinery wastes also have characteristics that constitute potential land, water and air pollutants. The disposal of wastes into the sea from oil facilities has direct effects on fish stocks.

The Impacts of Oil Pollution on the Environment and Wellbeing of the Ogoni People.

Oil pollution has impacted the Ogoni communities in several ways. These are grouped into three interrelated impacts:

1. Adverse impacts on Biodiversity
2. Socio-Economic Impacts
3. Physical-health impacts

THE IMPACT ON Ogoni BIODIVERSITY

The most profound and adverse impact of oil pollution in Ogoni, with far-reaching implications on all other aspects of the Ogoni's traditional lifestyles and livelihoods, has been the total loss of biodiversity and destruction of habitats largely due to soil degradation. The results of the unchecked oil pollution in Ogoni have been the destruction of ecosystems. Mangrove forests have fallen to the toxicity of oil spills and are being replaced by noxious nypa palms. The rainforest has fallen to the axe of oil companies, wildlife and game have been

driven away and farmlands have been rendered infertile with gross implications on the right to adequate food.

During oil spills, the process of photosynthesis, which enhances plant diversity, is impaired since the process is reduced because spilled crude has a high absorbance property, so when the crude spreads onto the surface of leaves, the latter find it difficult to photosynthesize and thus die, leading to biodiversity loss (Pyagbara, 2024). The toxic crude also affects underground herbs and shrubs, while microbial organisms, which form important groups in the food web, are also destroyed.

Socio-economic Impacts

These adverse impacts include: Nutritional styles and Food Shortage. One fallout of oil pollution in the Ogoni area is the destruction of the traditional local economic support system of fishing and farming. The combination of the effects of oil spills and acid rain resulting from gas flaring has led to soil degradation, which affects crop yield and harvest. Fish are driven away from inshore or shallow waters into deep-sea waters as a result of flaring. The ultimate result of this is the poor crop yield as the soil has been rendered infertile and poor fish catch, as most fish have been driven into deep waters, and the Ogoni people do not have the fishing gadgets to go into deep-sea fishing. The whole impact of this is food shortage and which has affected the ability of most families to feed themselves. As a result of the above, Ogoni which was once the food basket of the Niger Delta, is now fully dependent on imported food such as the popular icefish, which has now replaced the traditional fish in our menu table.

Thus, oil pollution has impacted the right to food of the Ogoni people. The African Commission (Decision 155/96, para 66 involving The Social and Economic Rights Action Center and the Center for Economic and Social Rights versus the Federal Republic of Nigeria) stated, amongst others that the government's treatment of the Ogoni has violated all three minimum duties of the right to food by allowing the IOCs to destroy food sources thereby falling short of what is expected, under the provisions of the African Charter and international human rights standards, and hence, is in violation of the right to food of the Ogoni (Pyagbara, 2024).

Destruction of Traditional Means of Livelihood

Another implication of oil pollution is that, having destroyed biodiversity, it has also rendered the agricultural sector, which is the largest employer of labour in Ogoni, unprofitable. Hence, most of the youths and women

have become jobless since their local economic support system of fishing and farming has been destroyed. An example is the case of the mangrove-abundant Ogoni community of Bodo, where the livelihood of the local people has been sustained by living in the midst of a once healthy and productive mangrove forest through fishing and farming. They also gathered mangrove wood for building and for local energy and fuel. However, due to being subjected to incessant oil spill incidents, oil has coated the breathing roots of this plant, killing off parts of the mangrove forest and animals and marine life that depend on it. This mangrove forest, which serves as a habitat for fish and the biodiversity in the creek as well as a source of raw materials for communities in Ogoni, have been lost to the ravages of oil pollution. The land, the sea and the environment can no longer support the subsistence life that this local Ogoni community which they have been dependent upon for thousands of years.

Migration and the Rise of Environmental Refugees

Socio-culturally, the Ogoni people live in closely knit communities and are more endogenous. The Ogoni people were not used to mass outflows/movement from their territory as their subsistent economy provided them with their basic needs. To the average Ogoni, movement from the area, which was considered a place of abundance into alien lands means subservience, poverty in the new area, and loss of pride and self-esteem. This indeed was not the situation before economic considerations led to the development intervention of oil exploration and exploitation by Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC), which resulted in a complete change in the socio-economic landscape of Ogoni. Oil pollution has resulted in the destruction of the Ogoni environment. This, in turn has led to the unsustainability of land for the traditional economic livelihood patterns that once thrived in the area. As a result, many Ogoni women and youths are emigrating out of the area into cities, especially to Port Harcourt, where they have become environmental refugees (Pyagbara, 2005) and because of their poor economic status, have had to take up accommodation in shanties, slums and waterfronts with its attendant risks, especially in terms of rights protection. In recent times, these slums have been facing demolitions by the government.

Physical-health Impacts of oil Pollution

Destruction of Zinc Roof

One of the increasing socio-economic costs to most Ogoni communities resulting from oil pollution is the rapidity with which zinc roofs are easily corroded. Houses with zinc roofs that are close to the location of the flare stacks do not last for two years before they become corroded. This is different from other areas where zinc roofs last for at least ten years. This is a common trend that is also observed in other parts of the Niger Delta where oil extraction is presently taking place (Pyagbara, 2024). This zinc corrosion has added another dimension to the increasing socio-economic costs to the burden of the Ogoni people. It is common knowledge that acid rain oxidizes zinc through the process of oxidation to form zinc oxides. This oxidation process is responsible for the corrosion. This has led Ogoni homeowners to resort to purchasing the expensive aluminium.

The Effects of Oil Pollution on Health

The most worrisome aspect of oil pollution in Ogoni is the rise in the occurrence of certain ailments that were previously unknown in the area. It has been reported that there is a correlation between exposure to oil pollution and the development of health problems (UNEP, 2011). In a recent research report released by a group of scientists from the Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Lagos, it was found that water samples collected from the sea, river, bore holes, lagoons, beach and so on from the Niger Delta region – especially in Delta and River States, indicates that more than 70% of the water in the Niger Delta contains a chemical called Benzo (a) pyrene, with a high concentration of 0.54 to 4ug per liter, far above the World Health Organization (WHO) recommendation of 0.7ug/l for drinking water (Bodo, 2018). The report further asserted that if the level of the harmful chemicals could be this high in ordinary water, the sediments which fish and other aquatic creatures feed on are definitely higher in Benzo pyrene concentration, and the people dependent on these marine creatures for food, automatically take in much higher levels of the cancerous chemical. This report is consistent with the experience that the Ogonis have had amongst their people in the past thirty years who had lived to see an increase in the occurrence of cancer and other respiratory problems traceable to oil pollution in the area. The diseases include respiratory problems, skin ailments such as rash and dermatitis, eye problems, gastro-intestinal disorders, water borne diseases and nutritional problems associated with poor diet (Mmon, 2025).

Effect on Underground Water

A serious threat posed by oil-related pollution is the impact on underground waters. When oil spills or when there is an effluent discharge or acid rain, it seeps into the ground and becomes mixed in the underground water system. It has been found that polluted underground water takes many years before it can be remedied. Yet this underground water moves into streams and wells which are the only sources of local water supply in the community which resulting in the rise of water-borne diseases. This has affected the traditional relationship of our people with water. There is a palpable fear that rather than being the source of life, these water systems have become sources of misery, disease and death.

THE OGONI UPRISING AND CIVIL DISOBEDIENCE

Exploration and production of crude oil started in Ogoni since 1956 and stopped abruptly in 1993. The presence of Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) in Ogoni for 50 years had destroyed the entire ecosystem (Pyagbara, 2024). At that point, it was no longer news that the entire Ogoni had been polluted as the late Ogoni Environmental activist Ken Saro-Wiwa took the campaign against the pollution of Ogoniland to the international community. This event led to widespread agitation in the entire Ogoni, as the people demanded that SPDC leave their land. The daily pressure and massive demonstration against SPDC resulted in violent attacks between the security agencies and the Ogoni youths. After several instances of SPDC access to their oil facilities by the host communities, it was finally shut down in 1993. This is a revolt against the Land Use Act of 1978. It is civil disobedience. It implies that the original owners of the land took it from those who took it by force under the guise of an immoral law. Even after the departure of SPDC in 1993, the pollution of the land continued, as the facilities were reported to be exposed, leading to frequent sabotage resulting in incessant fires, oil theft and operation of illegal refineries, leaving further massive environmental devastation in Ogoniland.

Consequently, there had been series of agitation and protests against the FGN for alleged environmental degradation and political alienation. It is on this premise that the FGN under President Obasanjo initiative a reconciliation process and in in July 2006, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) received an official request from the FGN to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the environmental and public health impacts of oil contamination in Ogoniland. In 2011, UNEP published an Environmental Assessment of

Ogoniland, popularly known as 'UNEP Report, a study of oil pollution in Ogoniland, in Rivers State, a region of the Niger Delta'.

Unfortunately, despite the capital-intensive reports and recommendations by UNEP, Ogoniland has remained polluted, and the people continue to conduct their businesses in a polluted environment. Hence, there had been more illnesses and deaths in the Ogoni communities daily. The people have assumed that their views and feelings about their environment have years of oil exploration has also resulted in impoverished communities.

PARADOX OF THE INTENDED PLAN FOR OIL RESUMPTION IN OGONI

Recent discussions and engagements have focused on the potential resumption of oil drilling in Ogoniland, after a period of suspension due to environmental concerns and community unrest. These discussions have been met with both support and opposition, with community members and activists raising concerns about environmental remediation, social justice, and the need for prior informed consent. With the Ogoni environment still under squalor and decay, it is a paradox that the Tinubu-led FGN requests an abrupt resumption without resolving the issues that led to the sudden halt in oil exploration. Many have envisaged that another level of conflict and uprising would hit Ogoni if either step on oil resumption is not retracted or utmost care is not taken in the dialogue process.

It is noteworthy to reiterate the breakdown of some salient key points:

- Oil exploration and production in Ogoniland were halted in 1993 due to unrest and protests against Shell's operations.
- The Ogoni people have long advocated for environmental remediation of their land, which has suffered from extensive oil spills and pollution.
- The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) has also highlighted the severe environmental damage in Ogoniland and recommended a comprehensive cleanup and remediation plan.

HYPREP, the Hydrocarbon Pollution Remediation Project, is an initiative by the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Environment to remediate the environmental damage caused by oil spills in Ogoniland. It is tasked with implementing the recommendations of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) report on the environmental assessment of Ogoniland. HYPREP's work includes soil and groundwater remediation, as well

as community development projects. HYPREP is still in the process of remediation but has not advanced significantly.

Recent Developments:

There have been recent meetings between the Nigerian president and Ogoni leaders to discuss the possibility of resuming oil drilling.

This has sparked debate, with some community members and activists expressing concerns about the lack of proper consultation and environmental safeguards.

The Corporate Accountability emphasizes the importance of "Nothing About Us Without Us" principle, advocating for the inclusion of Ogoni people in any discussions about oil drilling.

Some groups argue that the resumption of oil drilling is premature without a thorough cleanup and adequate environmental protection.

There are also concerns about the potential for further environmental degradation and the impact on the livelihoods of the Ogoni people.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Environmental Remediation:

The extent and effectiveness of cleanup efforts are crucial, as Ogoniland's environment has been severely impacted by past oil spills.

Community Engagement:

Ensuring the meaningful participation and consent of the Ogoni people in any decisions related to oil exploration and production is essential.

Social Justice:

The long-term impact on the livelihoods and well-being of the Ogoni people, including access to clean water and healthy food, needs to be carefully considered.

Alternative Livelihoods:

Providing sustainable alternative livelihood options for the Ogoni people is important, given the reliance on farming and fishing before oil operations were halted.

Transparency and Accountability:

There needs to be transparency and accountability in the management of oil resources and the implementation of environmental remediation plans.

Energy Transition

An energy transition refers to the shift from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources like solar, wind, and hydro power. The major structural change in how energy is produced and consumed aims to reduce carbon emissions and mitigate climate change. This transition involves not only technological changes but also shifts in energy infrastructure, policies, and societal behaviours. This is precisely what Ogoni needs now, not the resumption of oil exploitation. The debate surrounding oil extraction resumption in Ogoniland highlights the complex interplay between economic development, environmental protection, and social justice in the Niger Delta region.

CONCLUSION

It could be seen from the above that the externalities of oil extraction have resulted in profound adverse impacts on traditional lifestyles and livelihood patterns in the Ogoni community, where unchecked oil exploration and exploitation had taken place for the past fifty years. Aldo Leopold's Land Ethic expands the definition of "community" to include not only humans, but all of the other parts of the earth, as well: soils, waters, plants, and animals – "the land". In a Land Ethic, the relationships between people and land are intertwined; care for people cannot be separated from care for the land. Hence, care for the people of Ogoni should be holistic, a care that resonates not just the interest to explore their oil for profit making, but also a care for their environment in a venture that the communities in whose oil is extracted would have equal benefit with the explorers. It must be a win-win situation.

Aldo Leopold's concept of a Land Ethic transcends boundaries, speaking a universal language that resonates with individuals and communities across the globe. His ideas about respecting and ethically interacting with our natural environment continue to inspire and guide people, demonstrating that the principles of a Land Ethic are as pertinent and impactful today as they were when first articulated. This map illustrates the global footprint of the Land Ethic, highlighting the diverse array of countries whose citizens have connected with the Aldo Leopold philosophy. It is our measured opinion that to abate these adverse effects which oil pollution have had on the Ogoni Community, the oil companies and the government should show more commitment to the use of

imbibe Aldo Leopold's Land Ethic, the panacea to the abatement procedures and environmentally sound and cleaner technologies for oil exploration and exploitation. Just like it is done in Saudi Arabia, Russia, Canada, the United States, Iraq, the United Arab Emirates, Kuwait, and Norway without compromising the community ecosystem, the same measure is possible in Nigeria's Ogoni.

Finally, Leopold recognized that his dream of a widely accepted and implemented set of values based on caring for people, for land, and for all the connections between them – would have to “evolve... in the minds of a thinking community” (Leopold, 1949). Ogoni and all oil-bearing communities in the world are part of that thinking community. To shape a Land Ethic for the 21st century and beyond, Ogoni must engage in thoughtful dialogue with the FGN, inviting a diversity of perspectives, experiences, and backgrounds. Together, communities can form a Land Ethic that will live on to guide future generations. However, Communities must resist any form of land exploration when their interest are at stake. An energy transition is the best viable option in the 21st-century Ogoni.

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